

TRANSFORMATION OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN THE ERA OF GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract: The article examines the main aspects of globalization and its impact on the organization of scientific and educational processes. Special attention is paid to changes in international scientific cooperation, mobility of scientists and students, as well as adaptation of educational programs to the diversity of cultures and languages. The work helps to understand the modern challenges and opportunities facing science and education in the context of globalization.

Keywords: globalization, science, education, transformation, culture, educational and scientific processes, intercultural education.

In the era of globalization, education and upbringing become increasingly relevant and important as the world becomes more interconnected and diverse. Globalization demands that educational institutions pay more attention to intercultural education. This includes the development of programs aimed at studying various cultures, languages, and traditions to prepare students for successful adaptation in a multinational environment.

Intercultural education is an approach to education that aims to develop in students a respect for cultural diversity and the ability to effectively interact with members of different cultures. It seeks to overcome cultural stereotypes and prejudice, enriching the educational process with a diversity of perspectives and experiences from various cultures.

The main principles of intercultural education include:

1. Cultural Studies: Teaching students about cultural diversity, history, traditions, and values of different cultures.
2. Development of Intercultural Understanding: Helping students understand and appreciate the diversity of cultural experiences and perspectives.
3. Equal Learning Opportunities: Supporting equal participation of students from different cultural groups in the educational process.

4. Development of Intercultural Skills: Teaching communicative skills necessary for effective interaction with members of other cultures.

5. Overcoming Cultural Stereotypes and Prejudice: Supporting students in recognizing and overcoming biases and stereotypes that may hinder intercultural understanding.

Intercultural education emphasizes the importance of educating students for global citizenship and developing intercultural competence skills, which are increasingly crucial in a modern world where interactions between different cultures and nations are becoming more intense.

With the development of a global technological environment, education must actively incorporate innovative technologies into the learning process. This includes the use of online learning platforms, virtual reality, adaptive learning, and other modern methods to provide effective and accessible education for all.

Technological innovations in education play a key role in the modern world, especially in the era of globalization. Here are some of them:

1. Online Education and Distance Learning: Online education platforms provide students with the opportunity to receive education regardless of their location, expanding access to education and reducing geographical and social barriers.

2. Adaptive Learning: Adaptive learning technologies use machine learning algorithms to personalize the learning process according to each student's needs and abilities, making more efficient use of time and resources by considering individual learning styles.

3. Virtual and Augmented Reality: The use of virtual and augmented reality in education creates immersive learning environments where students can engage with visually and interactively rich educational materials, leading to deeper understanding and retention of information.

4. Blockchain in Education: Blockchain technology can be used to create secure and transparent systems for storing and verifying educational achievements, such as diplomas and certificates.

5. Interactive Whiteboards and Educational Apps: Interactive whiteboards and mobile educational apps provide students with access to interactive materials, gamified elements, and feedback mechanisms, making learning more engaging and effective.

6. Artificial Intelligence in Education: Artificial intelligence technologies can be used for analyzing learning data, creating personalized educational plans,

automating administrative processes, and developing intelligent agents to assist students in their studies.

Thus, technological innovations in education help make learning more accessible, effective, and engaging, while also preparing students for the digital economy and global society. Educational institutions should actively collaborate with international partners and develop student and faculty exchange programs. This allows students to broaden their horizons, explore other cultures and languages, and gain international experience. In the era of globalization, education must prepare students for the changing demands of the job market. This includes developing communication skills, intercultural interaction, digital literacy, and other skills necessary for a successful career on a global scale. Globalization poses new ethical and social challenges that education must address. This includes educating students about cultural diversity, respect for human rights, environmental responsibility, and other important values necessary for global citizenship. Educational institutions must actively engage in research and the development of teaching methods that respond to the challenges of globalization. This will help constantly improve the educational process and prepare students for future challenges. Overall, in the era of globalization, education plays a key role in the development of society and in preparing citizens for successful life and work on a global scale.

Globalization facilitates international exchange of research and knowledge. Scientists, researchers, and students gain access to information and resources from around the world, which contributes to the advancement of science and education. In the context of globalization, scientific and educational institutions actively collaborate internationally. This may include student and faculty exchanges, joint research projects, the creation of international education programs, and so on. Globalization poses new challenges for science and education, such as climate change, global security, poverty alleviation, and so on. Scientists and educational institutions must collaborate to develop solutions to these problems. On a global scale, interdisciplinary research becomes increasingly important. The use of information and communication technologies (ICT) is changing the formats of learning, research, and communication, opening up new opportunities and challenges. In the context of globalization, scientists and educated professionals face increasing competition in the global job market. Educational institutions must prepare students for this competition by developing high-level competencies and intercultural skills.

Overall, science and education play a key role in shaping a global society capable of addressing complex problems and striving for sustainable development. In the era of globalization, their interaction becomes increasingly intense and important for the development of the global community.

References:

1. Globalization and education: integration and contestation across cultures." *Journal of Education Policy*, 29(6), pp. 871–872
2. Odin, J. K., & Manicas, P. T. (Eds.). (2004). *Globalization and Higher Education*. University of Hawai'i Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt6wr3hj>
3. Štrajn, D. Globalization and education: Integration and contestation across cultures. *Int Rev Educ* 61, 121–124 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11159-014-9457-6>
4. Stromquist, N. P., & Monkman, Karen. (2000). *Globalization and education: integration and contestation across cultures* / edited by Nelly P. Stromquist and Karen Monkman. Rowman & Littlefield.